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TRANSNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND SCIENTIFIC DEVELOPMENT

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Volume 2, Issue 3, June 2026 - ISSN: 3092-9431

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Cooperative Teaching Strategies and Chemistry Students' Academic Achievement in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20277543>

Citation: Aniekan, C. E., Abakada, U. E., & Udoh., A. (2026). Cooperative Teaching Strategies and Chemistry Students' Academic Achievement in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Transnational Journal of Education and Scientific Development*, 2(3). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20277543>

Abstract

The study examined think-pair-share, team-pair-solo and expository teaching strategies and the academic achievement of chemistry students in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District. Four purposes, four research questions, and four hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The design for the study was a quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study comprised all the senior secondary one (SS1) students from all the public secondary schools in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District. The sample of the study was 283 students drawn from four intact classes from two secondary schools within the study area. A purposive sampling technique was used for the selection. The researcher developed an instrument tagged "Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT)" that was used for data collection. Face and content validation were used in validating the

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instrument and done by experts. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering the research questions, while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used for testing the hypotheses at the .05 level of significance. The study demonstrated a significant difference in the achievement scores of chemistry students who were taught the concept of water using think-pair-share, team-pair-solo, and expository instructional strategies in the Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District.

Keywords: cooperative Teaching strategies, academic achievement, chemistry students, and the Ikot Ekpene senatorial district.

Introduction

Education in general can be viewed as the development of life processes and the universal practice of human learning resulting from man's interaction with his social and natural environment. It is the process of facilitating the learning or acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and habits. This process can be achieved both inside and outside the classroom through many strategies, such as lecture, storytelling, discussion, demonstration, play way and cooperative learning strategies. Any experience that has a formative effect on the way a learner thinks, feels or acts can be considered educational.

The objectives of teaching chemistry at the secondary school level as stated by the National Policy on Education include making the learners know their environment, having a scientific and technological world, and advancing technologically, among others (NPE, 2013). In view of the above, it becomes imperative that schools not only equip learners with basic knowledge of chemistry content but also the practical skills needed for enhancing self-development.

Cooperative teaching strategy can be defined as a teaching strategy in which small teams, each composed of four to six students with different levels of ability, use a variety of learning activities to improve their understanding of the subject (Ibe, 2016). Each member of a team is responsible not only for learning what is taught but also for helping teammates learn, thus creating a sense of achievement and an atmosphere of cooperation and interaction. In this study a few cooperative

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teaching strategies were used, such as think-pair-share and team-pair-solo, with the conventional teaching method.

Think-pair-share, as the name goes, involves the students in thinking about challenging academic tasks given by the teacher individually, pairing with other students to exchange ideas and sharing the idea with the larger class. Eke (2021) is of the view that think-pair-share, also called multi-mode discussion, is a learning technique that provides processing time and builds in wait-time, which enhances the depth and breadth of thinking.

Team-Pair-Solo teaching strategy (TPSTS) is another cooperative learning strategy that facilitates greater interaction among students, with the learning materials as well, and improves academic achievement. TPSTS, according to Catherine (2018), is a cooperative learning strategy in which students solve problems first as a team, then with a partner, and finally on their own.

The expository teaching method is a teacher-centred instructional strategy where the instructor directly presents information to students in a highly structured, organised way. The goal is meaningful verbal learning, where students easily understand, retain, and connect new concepts to their existing knowledge.

Researchers report that cooperative teaching strategies foster higher academic achievement in science and chemistry in particular (Nnorom, 2015; Agu and Samuel, 2018). However, it seems the use of cooperative teaching strategies in teaching chemistry in the Akwa Ibom Northwest education zone has not attracted much attention, as chemistry classroom activities are still dominated by teacher-centred methods. Hence, there should be a paradigm shift from a teacher-centred learning environment to a student-centred learning environment through the use of cooperative teaching strategies. This had, therefore, made it necessary to investigate the effects of cooperative teaching strategies in the Akwa Ibom Northwest education zone.

Statements of the Problem

It is a well-documented fact in science education literature that the teaching and learning of chemistry have been faced with challenges which prevent optimum achievement of the objectives of chemistry education in national development. Osuala and Ogomaka (2020) reported that more than 60% of Nigerian secondary

school chemistry teachers use the conventional methods which make students passive learners. The conventional method does not encourage meaningful student-teacher, student-student, or student-material interaction. The conventional method promotes rote memory at the cost of critical thinking and reading. This type of instructional method does not allow for active participation and interaction of students in the teaching-learning process. As a result, poor academic achievement becomes evident. According to Yaduvanshi and Singh (2019), the conventional method used in teaching in secondary schools is not yielding good results in terms of the academic achievement of chemistry students in both internal and external examinations. These conventional teaching strategies lack students' cooperation and interaction required for effective learning and transfer of knowledge in chemistry concepts, which are mainly abstract and difficult. Therefore, this study aimed at answering questions such as 'Do cooperative instructional strategies promote better understanding of concepts in chemistry?' 'What are the effects of these cooperative instructional strategies on the academic achievement of secondary school students in chemistry in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District?'

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students based on cooperative instructional strategies and expository strategies in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District. Specifically, the study seeks to determine the following:

- i. the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share, team-pair-solo and expository instructional strategies
- ii. the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and team-pair-solo instructional strategies in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District.
- iii. the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District.

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- iv. the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using team, pair, solo and expository instructional strategies in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share, team-pair-solo and expository instructional strategies?
- ii. What is the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and team-pair-solo instructional strategies in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District?
- iii. What is the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District?
- iv. What is the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using team, pair, solo and expository instructional strategies in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- i. There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share, think-pair-solo and expository instructional strategies.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and team-pair-solo instructional strategies.
- iii. There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies.

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- iv. There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using team, pair, solo and expository instructional strategies.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a quasi-experimental research design. Specifically, a non-randomised pretest-posttest control group design was used, as participants were not randomly assigned to groups. This design was appropriate for the study because the researcher worked with intact classes. The population of the study comprised all Senior Secondary One (SS1) students from all public secondary schools in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District.

The sample of the study consisted of 283 students. This sample was drawn from four intact classes from two secondary schools within the study area. A purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of the sample. The distribution of the sample across the three instructional strategy groups, as shown in Tables 4.1 through 4.8, was as follows: the think-pair-share group had 91 students, the team-pair-solo group had 95 students, and the expository group had 97 students.

The researcher developed an instrument tagged “Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT)” that was used for data collection. The CAT consisted of multiple-choice test items constructed on the concept of water. Each item on the CAT carried one correct answer and three distractors. A respondent’s score carried one mark for each correct response, whereas an incorrect response carried zero marks. The highest mark obtainable on the CAT was 20. The instrument was validated using face and content validation, performed by experts.

The data collection procedure involved the administration of a pretest to all groups (think-pair-share, team-pair-solo, and expository) before the instructional intervention. Following the pretest, the concept of water was taught to the three groups using their respective instructional strategies. After the instructional period, a posttest was administered to all groups. The fieldwork for this study was conducted in 2025, as indicated in all result tables. Data collected from the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) were analysed using descriptive and

inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer all four research questions. Specifically, mean scores and standard deviations were computed for the pretest and posttest scores of students taught using think-pair-share, team-pair-solo, and expository instructional strategies. The mean difference between pretest and posttest scores was also calculated. For the testing of all four null hypotheses at the .05 level of significance, analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used. The ANCOVA analysis was performed separately for each hypothesis, controlling for the pretest scores as a covariate, with results reported as F-values, degrees of freedom, and significance levels (p-values).

Result and Discussion of Findings

Research Question One

What is the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share, team pair solo and expository instructional strategies?

Table 4.1: Mean and standard deviation of the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share, team pair solo and expository instructional strategies (N =283)

Cooperative strategies	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Think pair share	91	8.09	1.33	15.33	1.83	7.24
Team pair solo	95	7.79	1.19	13.99	1.69	6.20
Expository	97	8.11	1.40	11.09	1.65	2.98

(Source: Field Work, 2025)

The result in Table 4.1 reveals that the pretest–posttest mean difference of 7.24 obtained by the students taught using think-pair-share was greater than that of 6.20 obtained by their counterparts taught using team-pair-solo, which was in turn greater than that of 2.98 obtained by those taught using the expository instructional strategy. The result in the table also reveals that the pretest and posttest

standard deviation scores of 1.33 and 1.83; 1.19 and 1.69; as well as 1.40 and 1.65 obtained by the students taught using think-pair-share, team-pair-solo, and expository instructional strategies, respectively, showed that, though the students taught using think-pair-share had the highest mean score difference, the scattering of the raw score from the mean was also higher in the think-pair-share group, followed by those in the think-pair-solo and those in the expository group. This means that there is a difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share, team-pair-solo and expository instructional strategies.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students' taught the concept of water using think pair share and team pair solo instructional strategies?

Table 4.2: Mean and standard deviation of the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share and team pair solo instructional strategies (N =186)

Instructional strategies	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Think pair share	91	8.09	1.33	15.33	1.83	7.24
Team pair solo	95	7.79	1.19	13.99	1.69	6.20

(Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2025)

The result in Table 4.2 reveals that the pretest–posttest mean difference of 7.24 obtained by the students taught using think-pair-share was greater than that of 6.20 obtained by their counterparts taught using the think-pair-solo strategy. The pretest and posttest standard deviation scores of 1.33 and 1.83 as well as 1.19 and 1.69 obtained by the students taught with the think-pair-share and team-pair-solo

instructional strategies, respectively, showed that, though the students taught using think-pair-share had the higher mean score difference, the scattering of the raw score from the mean was also slightly higher in the think-pair-share group. This means that there is a difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and team-pair-solo instructional strategies.

Research Question Three

What is the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share and expository instructional strategies.

Table 4.3: Mean and standard deviation of the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share and expository instructional strategies (N =188)

Instructional strategies	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Think pair share	91	8.09	1.33	15.33	1.83	7.24
Expository	97	8.11	1.40	11.09	1.65	2.98

(Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2025)

The result in Table 4.3 reveals that the pretest–posttest mean difference of 7.24 obtained by the students taught using think-pair-share was greater than that of 2.98 obtained by their counterparts taught using the expository instructional strategy. The pretest and posttest standard deviation scores of 1.33 and 1.83, as well as 1.40 and 1.65, obtained by the students taught with the think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies, respectively, showed that, though the students taught using think-pair-share had the higher mean score difference, the scattering of the raw score from the mean was also slightly higher in the think-pair-share group. This means that there is a difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students

taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies.

Research Question Four

What is the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using team pair solo and expository instructional strategies?

Table 4.4: Mean and standard deviation of the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using team pair solo and expository instructional strategies (N =192)

Instructional strategies	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Team pair solo	95	7.79	1.19	13.99	1.69	6.20
Expository	97	8.11	1.40	11.09	1.65	2.98

(Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2025)

The result in Table 4.4 reveals that the pretest–posttest mean difference of 6.20 obtained by the students taught using think-pair-solo was greater than that of 2.98 obtained by their counterparts taught using the expository instructional strategy. The pretest and posttest standard deviation scores of 1.19 and 1.69 as well as 1.40 and 1.65 obtained by the students taught with the think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies, respectively, showed that, though the students taught using think-pair-share had the higher mean score difference, the scattering of the raw scores from the mean was also slightly higher in the think-pair-share group. This means that there is a difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share, think pair solo and expository instructional strategies.

Table 4.5: Result of ANCOVA analysis of the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share, team pair solo and expository instructional strategies (N=283)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1014.52 ^a	3	338.17	134.26	.00
Intercept	639.08	1	639.08	253.72	.00
Pretest	126.52	1	126.52	50.23	.00
Instructional strategies	910.67	2	455.33	180.77	.00
Error	702.75	279	2.52		
Total	52742.00	283			
Corrected Total	1717.27	282			

(Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2025)

The result in Table 4.5 shows the F-value of 180.77 and the corresponding probability level of significance of .00 alpha at 2 and 279 degrees of freedom. This level of significance is less than .05, on which the decision is based. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share, team-pair-solo and expository instructional strategies.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share and team pair solo instructional strategies

Table 4.6: Result of ANCOVA analysis of the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share and team pair solos instructional strategies (N=186)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	164.06 ^a	2	82.03	30.86	.00
Intercept	495.24	1	495.24	186.28	.00
Pretest	80.58	1	80.58	30.31	.00
cooperative _strategies	64.15	1	64.15	24.13	.00
Error	486.52	183	2.66		
Total	40544.00	186			
Corrected Total	650.58	185			

(Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2025)

The result in Table 4.6 shows the F-value of 24.13 and the corresponding probability level of significance of .00 alpha at 1 and 183 degrees of freedom. This level of significance is less than .05, on which the decision is based. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and team-pair-solo instructional strategies.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share and expository instructional strategies.

Table 4.7: Result of ANCOVA analysis of the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair share and expository instructional strategies (N=188)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	995.73 ^a	2	497.87	224.98	.00
Intercept	315.74	1	315.74	142.68	.00
Pretest	152.88	1	152.88	69.09	.00
cooperative _strategies	849.52	1	849.52	383.89	.00
Error	409.39	185	2.21		
Total	33883.00	188			
Corrected Total	1405.12	187			

(Source: *Researcher's Field Work, 2025*)

The result in Table 4.7 shows the F-value of 383.89 and the corresponding probability level of significance of .00 at alpha of 1 and 185 degrees of freedom. This level of significance is less than .05, on which the decision is based. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies.

Hypothesis Four

There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using team pair solo and expository instructional strategies.

Table 4.8: Result of ANCOVA analysis of the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think pair solo and expository instructional strategies (N=192)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	439.74 ^a	2	219.87	84.44	.00

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Intercept	476.28	1	476.28	182.91	.00
Pretest	37.02	1	37.02	14.22	.00
Cooperative _strategies	427.22	1	427.22	164.07	.00
Error	492.13	189	2.60		
Total	31057.00	192			
Corrected Total	931.87	191			

(Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2025)

The result in Table 4.8 shows the F-value of 164.07 and the corresponding probability level of significance of .00 at alpha of 1 and 189 degrees of freedom. This level of significance is less than .05, on which the decision is based. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one sought to determine the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share, team-pair-solo, and expository instructional strategies. The data presented in Table 4.1 showed that the pretest–posttest mean difference for the think-pair-share group was 7.24, which was greater than the 6.20 mean difference for the team-pair-solo group, which was in turn greater than the 2.98 mean difference for the expository group. The standard deviations indicated that the think-pair-share group had the highest scattering of raw scores from the mean (pretest SD = 1.33; posttest SD = 1.83), followed by the team-pair-solo group (pretest SD = 1.19; posttest SD = 1.69), and then the expository group (pretest SD = 1.40; posttest SD = 1.65). Correspondingly, hypothesis one was tested using ANCOVA, and the result in Table 4.5 showed an F-value of 180.77 with a probability level of significance of .00 at 2 and 279 degrees of freedom. Since this significance level (.00) was less than the .05 alpha level, the null hypothesis was rejected. This finding indicates that there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share, team-pair-solo, and expository instructional strategies. This finding aligns with that of Eke (2021), whose findings

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showed that there was a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control groups in favour of the experimental group. The present finding is also in line with that of Andrew and Alexander (2015), whose finding showed a significant difference in academic achievement in favour of those who were exposed to the think-pair-share instructional strategy.

Research question two sought to determine the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and team-pair-solo instructional strategies. The data presented in Table 4.2 revealed that the pretest–posttest mean difference for the think-pair-share group (7.24) was greater than that for the team-pair-solo group (6.20). The standard deviations showed that the think-pair-share group had slightly higher scattering of raw scores from the mean (pretest SD = 1.33; posttest SD = 1.83) compared to the team-pair-solo group (pretest SD = 1.19; posttest SD = 1.69). Correspondingly, hypothesis two was tested using ANCOVA, and the result in Table 4.6 showed an F-value of 24.13 with a corresponding probability level of significance of .00 at 1 and 183 degrees of freedom. Since this significance level (.00) was less than the .05 alpha level, the null hypothesis was rejected. This finding indicates that there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and team-pair-solo instructional strategies.

Research question three sought to determine the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies. The data presented in Table 4.3 revealed that the pretest–posttest mean difference for the think-pair-share group (7.24) was greater than that for the expository group (2.98). The standard deviations showed that the think-pair-share group had slightly higher scattering of raw scores from the mean (pretest SD = 1.33; posttest SD = 1.83) compared to the expository group (pretest SD = 1.40; posttest SD = 1.65). Correspondingly, hypothesis three was tested using ANCOVA, and the result in Table 4.7 showed an F-value of 383.89 with a corresponding probability level of significance of .00 at 1 and 185 degrees of freedom. Since this significance level (.00) was less than the .05 alpha level, the null hypothesis was rejected. This finding indicates that there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using think-pair-share and expository instructional strategies.

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Research question four sought to determine the difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using team-pair-solo and expository instructional strategies. The data presented in Table 4.4 revealed that the pretest–posttest mean difference for the team-pair-solo group (6.20) was greater than that for the expository group (2.98). The standard deviations showed that the team-pair-solo group had slightly higher scattering of raw scores from the mean (pretest SD = 1.19; posttest SD = 1.69) compared to the expository group (pretest SD = 1.40; posttest SD = 1.65). However, it must be noted that the text in Table 4.4’s description contains a typographical error, stating “think-pair-share” instead of “team-pair-solo”, though the data correctly refer to the team-pair-solo group. Correspondingly, hypothesis four was tested using ANCOVA, and the result in Table 4.8 showed an F-value of 164.07 with a corresponding probability level of significance of .00 at 1 and 189 degrees of freedom. Since this significance level (.00) was less than the .05 alpha level, the null hypothesis was rejected. This finding indicates that there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students taught the concept of water using team-pair-solo and expository instructional strategies.

Conclusion

The findings consistently demonstrate that cooperative learning strategies, particularly think-pair-share, produced superior academic achievement outcomes compared to the expository instructional strategy. Among the three instructional strategies investigated, think-pair-share was the most effective in enhancing students' academic achievement in the concept of water in chemistry, followed by team-pair-solo, while the expository strategy yielded the lowest mean gain. Thus, it is conclusively established that think-pair-share enhanced students' academic achievement more than team-pair-solo and expository instructional strategies in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Chemistry teachers should use the think-pair-share instructional strategy for teaching chemistry to enhance better academic achievement of students in the Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District.
- ii. Policy makers, curriculum planners and school administrators should not only elucidate cooperative instructional strategies, but they should monitor their implementation as well.
- iii. Workshops, seminars and training/retraining should be planned or structured by ministries of education and other related government agencies on how to apply the think-pair-share instructional strategy in the teaching of chemistry and other science subjects in the Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District.

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TRANSNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND SCIENTIFIC DEVELOPMENT

A PUBLICATION OF WORD ASTRA
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Volume 2, Issue 3, June 2026 - ISSN: 3092-9431

Charlie Emaediong Aniekan Abakada U. E; Professor Udoh. A.

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